

Process Development to Realize All-Semiconductor InGaP-GaAs based Photonic-Crystal Surface Emitting Lasers

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The photonic crystal surface emitting laser (PCSEL) is a type of semiconductor laser with an embedded two-dimensional photonic crystal (PC) in order to provide large area two-dimensional distributed feedback in the plane of the laser and its output coupling into useful surface emission. Combining the properties of both edge emitting and vertical cavity surface emitting lasers, PCSELS allow the scaling of devices to large areas for high power operation [1]. Based on theoretical findings published in [2] we started to develop the fabrication process to realize PCSELS, and we herein focus on the integration of the embedded PCs, which is the most critical technological step.

The PCSEL configuration addressed here is depicted in Figure 1(a). The single lattice unit cell consists of a triangle feature as shown in Figure 1(b) with a lattice constant $a \cong 320$ nm, designed for an emission wavelength around 1070 nm. The first epitaxial growth with metalorganic vapor phase epitaxy (MOVPE) on a n-GaAs substrate ends with an InGaP layer. The PCs are introduced into the InGaP through (i) e-beam lithography, (ii) inductively coupled plasma reactive ion etching (ICP-RIE) followed by (iii) MOVPE overgrowth to complete the epitaxial layer structure of the PCSEL.

(i) We found that hydrogen silsesquioxane (HSQ) resist is a better suited technology not only because it offers higher resolution but especially because HSQ resist removal results in a clean surface that is well suited for subsequent overgrowth. Here, we show results on optimizing the HSQ process to allow for the following ICP-RIE step. For relatively thick HSQ, we studied different concentrations of Tetramethyl Ammonium Hydroxide (TMAH) for the development and found that side walls as well as the contrast of the resist are best for our work when the concentration of TMAH is high. The recipe allows a 40 nm wide gap between two consecutive triangles to be realized [3]. Although the exposure dose increased to large values, we achieved reasonable writing times for our full PCSEL layout on 3-inch wafers. Figure 2 shows top-down SEM images of the triangles in HSQ resist on InGaP.

(ii) We performed ICP-RIE for the resist to InGaP transfer. In order to precisely control the ~150 nm etch depth with minimum damage to the quantum well (QW), just 50 nm below the PC layer, we applied very low RF power at a high temperature. An in-situ interferometer was used to stop the etching when InGaP was etched through. Ar was used to obtain a dilute process with stable plasma ignition. BCl₃ was added to achieve slow and controllable ICP etching. Figure 3(a) showcases an SEM image of triangles taken after the RIE process with the etch recipe developed in this work.

(iii) After HSQ resist removal, followed by a cleaning step, the InGaP pillars were overgrown with MOVPE. The cross-section SEM picture of the overgrown InGaP pillars is shown in Figure 3(b).

The absence of morphological defects and planarized GaAs confinement layers allow the overgrowth of the remaining structure. The presented results pave the way for the fabrication of PCSELS with all-semiconductor integrated gratings with high optical coupling.

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- [2] M. Radziunas et al., "Optical mode calculation in large-area photonic crystal surface-emitting lasers" *IEEE Photon. J.*, 16 (2024), doi: 10.1109/JPHOT.2024.3380532
- [3] X. Yang et al., "Challenges in 1 Teradot/in.² dot patterning using electron beam lithography for bit-patterned media", *Vac Sci Technol B.* 25 (2007), doi: 10.1116/1.2798711

Figure 1. (a) Schematics of a PCSEL cross section and (b) top view of the photonic crystal layer

Figure 2. (a) HSQ resist (thickness 400 nm): top-down SEM images of 100 μm circle consisting of triangle arrays and (b) array of PCSEL triangles developed with TMAH 25%

Figure 3. (a) SEM image of top view of PCSEL triangles after RIE process and (b) Cross-section SEM image of a fully fabricated buried PCSEL arrays